

Magnetic Displacement Sensor Based Elevator Weight Measurement

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Abstract – Elevator is famous and common way for vertical transporting. Today, elevator traffic management systems are so important to reduce energy and time losses. In order to obtain time and prevent energy losses, elevator weight must be measure and control strategies must regard the weight. There are two classical methods to measure the weight. one of them works as one of and the other is based on real load cells. In this study a novel method is offered to measure elevator weight regarding easy installing and calibrating. In this study, high resolution magnetic displacement sensor is designed and characterized for elevator application. Magnetic displacement sensor is sensitive to magnetic field changing. In this study, 1cm distance are calibrated as 1000kg and output generates 0-10V voltage related to distance. Inside the sensor includes FIR sensor to reduces fluctuating. Because elevator includes rubber spring to reduce mechanical noise and shaking.

Keywords – Magnetic displacement sensor, elevator weight, hall effect, FIR filter, Analog to Digital Converter

I. INTRODUCTION

Elevator control strategies are focused on energy efficiency and minimum waiting time for users. In order to improve the control, strategies use many parameters to manage the elevator such as door opening time, fast doors, human sensing sensor and etc. But without the knowing elevator weight, all strategies are fragile. Another parameter to improve control strategies is measuring the weight of people inside the cabin [1-3]. So, control algorithm can made sophisticated calculation during the working especially for group elevators applications. Which elevator move or which one pass without stopping. Measuring the weight in elevators, there are two classical methods. One of them is includes switch just generates “elevator is overload” and “elevator is empty”. On the contrary, loadcell based method gives “how much elevator is full”. On the contrary loadcell have to be used four pieces on the four corners to measure. So switched model is adequate

but cheap. Loadcell is expensive and need four pieces. In this study, magnetic displacement sensor is specialized for elevator to measure weight. this sensor merges benefits of classical methods as simplicity and easy installing and calibrating.

Magnetic field sensors are based on hall effect behavior of current flow. DC constant current flows smoothly and uses all area of conductor [4,5]. Figure 1 shows current flow on a sheet.

Figure 1. Hall effect sensor principle (a) without any magnetic excitation (b) During the magnet exposed

Without any magnetic field, current density is same all section. Because of zero frequency. At any magnetic field is exposed this sheet, current density is changed and relocated according to magnetic field magnitude. During this reshaping the current flow generates perpendicular voltage related to magnetic magnitude. Generated voltage is DC and corelated with the magnetic field. In this study, thermal drift is not considered. Linear hall effect sensor has middle point for steady state and magnet direction sensitive [6,7]. Figure 2. Shows linear hall effect characteristic.

Figure 2. Hall effect sensor

$$V_H = \frac{I_x B_z}{n e t} \tag{Equ. (1)}$$

Where; V_H generated voltage, I_x current flows on x axis, B_z created magnetic field by magnet, n charge density, e electron charge and t thickness.

In this study, N and S magnet sides characterized to be free from directions. So even S or N side are closed, Sensor gives same signal magnitude.

Analog Digital Conversation (ADC) is a secret gate which is connecting analog world to digital world. Digital world is fast robust but not continuous. On the contrary analog world is sensitive but continuous

[8,9]. Analog signals can be transferred to digital word via ADC. There are 2 main parameters to choose right ADC. Figure 4 shows any analog signal conversation.

Figure 3. Signal processing in this study

From 4, x line related to timing and explain the sample rate. How many pieces of signal can be executed in a second. On the contrary, y axis says how many pieces analog signal is sliced. It means number of bits or bytes. Any ordinary microcontroller has 12-14 bits ADC unit[10,11].

Any sensor signal can be filtered in case of being noisy. In this study especially focused on FIR filter to obtain high grade quality. FIR filter is so common in literature to filter to signals [12-14]. Finite response filter (FIR) is digitally controllable and it is so easy to change its parameters. During the elevator weight measuring, 1 second response time is accepted as logical in empirical tests. FIR filter design is configured 100 pieces parts and 1 second period to repeat. Figure 4 shows FIR filter structure.

Figure 4. FIR filter structure

Where Fig. 4,

$$t = x(n) - x(n-1) \rightarrow 10\text{mSec}$$

$$k_0, \dots, k_{99} = 1/100 \text{ constant}$$

After FIR filter, All calculation is inside to microcontroller and need to be visible via environmental units such as DAC. DAC is a bit different from ADC and not easy to see high resolution like ADC [15-16]. So according to request, DAC can be created R-2R or $R \times 2^n$ structure. Generally, R-2R is common and easy way to do. For number of small bits, R-2n structure can be simple [17,18]. In this study, 12 bits DAC configures to match 12 bits ADC.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Elevator weight measuring structure has been based on magnetic displacement sensor. For this application 17000 gauss magnet has been used. Figure 5 shows the strategy of proposed measuring method.

Figure 5. Proposed system structure

For maximum distance, generated voltage is zero and one bipolar led blinking green. led indicates the running and no low magnet level. When the magnet close to sensor, output signal level increase and when reached the empty point of cabin weight, (at the same time this point is calibration point for empty cabin), blinking led turns to half green and half red blinking. This voltage level was settled as 2.5Volt. this voltage guides the application engineer to grab the first right point. If there is much closer magnet to sensor, led turns to red blinking and led turns to all red. It means over weight thus over flow occurred. Measured voltage levels related to distance may be not linear. In case of the nonlinear measuring a correction, algorithm was applied. Figure 6(a) shows nonlinear sample data and Figure 6 (b) is corrected on. Microcontroller has discussed ADC and DAC include inside such as STM32F030. STM series microcontrollers are arm-based structure so have many useful environmental and adequate speed for many kinds of applications [19,20].

Amplifier section is classical operational amplifier designed as non-inverting. It turns to maximum value to 10V output analog level.

Figure 6. Proposed system structure

Op-amp was chosen as wide range powered and temperature gap such as LM324. Op-amp was powered under single supply and R_f as 10K and R_g as 4.7K were used. According to R_f and R_g , K_v can be calculated using Equ. 2.

$$K_v = 1 + \frac{R_f}{R_g} \tag{Equ (1)}$$

K_v can be obtained as 3,12 and maximum DAC output close to 3.3V, thus maximum op-amp output can be calculated as

$$3.12 \times 3.3 = 10.3 \text{ Volt}$$

C_f is need to be avoided in case of self-oscillating and obtained smooth output.

Figure 7. Obtained graphics after linearization

Hall effect theoretically gives linear voltage level because of the current source working principles. But environmental conditions may make distortion or deterioration on the linear output curve. Figure 7 shows final output signal from specialized sensor. Figure 8a and Figure 8b shows first designed sensor under test and after the mass production.

(a) (b)
Figure 8. Obtained graphics after linearization

In Finally, a commercial sensor was designed for the elevator industry that is easy to install and provides a 0-10 volts output with a long cable. In particular, the aim was to prevent possible usage errors by linearizing the output.

III. RESULTS

In this study, A novel sensor based on magnetic displacement measurement is specialized for elevator applications. High resolution and analogue output can be characterized for easy installation and more just one piece is enough to measure. The obtained resolution was measured lower 5kg weight at real application.

Obtained results are adequate to use in elevator industry. Normal cabin can yawn around 1 or 2 centimeters during the loading. This sensor measures the rubber yawning during the loading.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study offers a new style sensor to measure elevator weight with one sensor. Magnetic displacement sensors are very common to obtain data. On the other hand, elevator cabins contain a number of obstacles that will make the application of the sensor difficult. Magnetic displacement sensor are specialized for elevator industry increasing resolution and adding FIR filter and output protection. 0-10 Volts output and response time is arranged as 1 second.

V. CONCLUSION

Magnetic sensors are very common in literature and most of the solutions can be seen in many areas. In this study, magnetic displacement sensor was specialized for elevator applications. There are two kinds method to measure elevator cabin weight. One of is simple and just include a switch. Second one needs 4 point to install but has good resolution. Offered method merges one switch convenience and four point resolution. Sensor has 0-10Volts analogue output ability and 1 second response time. In future, sensor can be applied in heavy vehicle to measure there's load.

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